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Clinical Pharmaceutical Care in Nursing Home Residents as a Cornerstone for Drug-Related Problems Identification

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Received: 4 September 2024 | **Revised:** 23 February 2025 | **Accepted:** 31 March 2025

Funding: This work was supported by The Ministry of Health, Czech Republic—Conceptual Development of Research Organization (NNH, 00023884) and the project New Technologies for Translational Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences (NETPHARM, project ID CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004607), co-funded by the European Union.

Keywords: clinical pharmacy | drug-related side effects and adverse reactions | inappropriate prescribing | older people | polypharmacy

ABSTRACT

Rational prescribing in geriatrics represents an important ethical as well as socio-economic issue. The aim of this project was to analyze the drug-related problems (DRPs) among the Czech nursing home residents and increase public awareness of further possible employment of clinical pharmacists in social care. The project was designed as a multicenter observational study. A total of 16 nursing homes and 800 participants with an average age of 84.6 ± 7.3 years were included in the study. Of them, a DRP was noted in 93.3% of people. The total amount of DRPs identified was 2215, which means an average of 2.8 ± 1.6 DRPs per patient. The most common DRPs identified were ‘overtreatment’ (19.5%), ‘undertreatment’ (12.8%), inappropriate dose (10.6%), recommendations for laboratory monitoring (10.4%) and adverse effects (10.3%). Of different drug classes, BZDs (OR 16.6, 95% CI 1.0–270.2), PPIs (OR 2.5, 95% CI 1.1–5.6) and NSAIDs (OR 4.4, 95% CI 1.1–18.3) were identified to be most commonly associated with DRPs. The risk of DRP identification clearly increased with the number of drugs used, with seven drugs demonstrated as the best cut-off for predicting DRP identification (AUC 0.842, sensitivity 0.602; specificity 0.796). ‘SENIOR’ project has confirmed a high rate of excessive polypharmacy among nursing home residents in the Czech republic resulting in high risk of potential and manifested DRPs. The project emphasized the role of clinical pharmacists in optimizing safety and effectiveness of treatment among older nursing home residents.

1 | Introduction

Rational prescribing in geriatrics represents an important ethical as well as socio-economic issue. As a result of individual changes accompanying aging, the functional reserves

are gradually depleted and the adaptive abilities and organ functions deteriorate. With growing age, the number of diseases, particularly chronic and degenerative, displaying peculiarities in their course and symptomatology increases [1]. Changes in target tissues sensitivity, reduced gut absorption

Abbreviations: BDZ, benzodiazepines; DRPs, drug-related problems; NSAIDs are, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs; PPIs, proton-pump inhibitors.

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Summary

- What is the current knowledge on the topic?
 - Prescribing for older patients presents unique challenges. The problem of inappropriate and unsafe prescribing among elderly people places them at risk of excessive polypharmacy and subsequent drug-related problems (DRPs).
- What question did this study address?
 - We aimed to analyze the DRPs among older nursing home residents and to identify the drugs most commonly associated with their occurrence.
- What does this study add to our knowledge?
 - Among community-dwelling older people, we revealed an alarmingly high rate of excessive polypharmacy with a clear association with DRP occurrence. The number of drugs with the best predictive value for DRP occurrence was seven or more. Namely, benzodiazepines/Z-hypnotics, proton-pump inhibitors, and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs prescriptions put the older patients at high risk of DRP occurrence.
- How might this change clinical pharmacology or translational science?
 - Our findings call for the need for regular medication review and suitable monitoring among older nursing home residents. The project has emphasized the role of clinical pharmacists in optimizing the safety and effectiveness of treatment in this population.

of some drugs, and limited function of eliminating organs in older people result in pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics changes, more frequent adverse effects manifestation, and other drug-related problems (DRPs). Polymorbidity and polypragmasia increase the risk of drug–drug interactions and non-adherence to therapy. These above-mentioned aspects could be expressed as a change in the therapeutic value of drugs [2]. The increasing age and the amount of drugs used represent significant independent risk factors for drug-induced complications. Among the patients over 70 years, the occurrence of adverse effects of drugs has increased 5-fold compared to the population aged between 20 and 40 years (from 4% to 21%) [3]. A correlation was also observed between the occurrence of adverse effects and the number of drugs used; the patients taking 10 drugs or more were reported to have an 8-fold higher risk of undesirable effects when compared to the population using 1–2 medicaments [4]. A higher amount of drugs prescribed to polymorbid patients increases the risk of inappropriate prescription [5], drug–drug interactions, drug–disease interactions, adverse drug-induced reactions, and medication errors. All these individual aspects are very closely connected and interrelated [6, 7]. A notion “prescription cascade” describes the situation when a wrong assessment of drug adverse effects, not recognizing them as such, results in the prescription of additional therapeutics in an effort to manage these effects [8]. This approach contributes to irrational polypharmacotherapy and exacerbates its consequences. It has been estimated that 35% of older adults have experienced drug adverse effects even though the number of these events could potentially be reduced up to a half

[9]. In the Czech Republic, older people make up 13.5% of the population, but they consume 35%–45% of all drug expenses [10]. Additional considerable costs are spent for unnecessary and repeated hospitalizations related to drug-induced reactions. According to a British study from the 1990s, one-fifth of hospitalizations among older people was due to inadequate pharmacotherapy, while half of these cases could have been efficiently avoided [11].

Medication of older patients requires a specific approach, strict individualization, simple drug regimen, selection of a drug with the best safety profile, and regular subsequent checks of the patient's clinical condition hand to hand with an expected life expectancy and quality of life [2]. Great efforts have been expended worldwide to bring the accepted procedures closer to prescribing physicians and allow their use in clinical practice. Standard criteria for defining drugs potentially inappropriate for older adults were issued at the beginning of the 1990s in response to the high occurrence of risk prescriptions in the US nursing homes [12]. These ‘Beers criteria’ had been repeatedly revised and updated and gradually became a synonym for appropriate or inappropriate prescription in older adults. In the European context, the clinical practice often prefers the STOPP/START criteria (2008), originating from the analysis of pharmacotherapy of geriatric patients at the university hospital in Cork, Ireland [13]. The STOPP (Screening Tool of Older Persons' Prescriptions) criteria is an expert consensus presenting a list of drugs often prescribed inadequately whose adverse effects in the elderly may be severe (e.g., deterioration of cognitive functions, orthostatic hypotension, increased risk of falls). In contrast, the START (Screening Tool to Alert to Right Treatment) criteria define the drugs or drug groups with demonstrated benefits that should not be missing in geriatric medication. Based on the international guidance and also taking into account specifics of the Czech drug market and prescription patterns, the Czech expert consensus regarding the drugs potentially inappropriate in advanced age was introduced in 2012 [8].

To this day, many works have documented high rates of DRPs among the older nursing home residents; however, the pharmacotherapy situation in nursing homes has not been adequately studied. The only study analyzing the issue of pharmacotherapy in nursing homes in the Czech Republic was completed in 2014 by professor Vlček [14]. Monitoring was done in two nursing homes and included 58 respondents. The average number of drugs used by the clients was 8.9 prescription-only medicaments, 1.2 over-the-counter medicines, and 0.6 nutrient supplements. Potential drug–drug interactions were revealed in 86% of respondents. Severe and very severe drug interactions were found in 8.6% of respondents, and medication inappropriate in elderly was prescribed to 65% of patients included.

In an effort to react to this alarming situation, non-profit organization ‘Institute of the Drug Guide’ decided to analyze pharmacotherapy in older nursing home residents in different regions of the Czech Republic. The role of the expert partner for assessing medication was accepted by the ‘Department of Clinical Pharmacy of Na Homolce Hospital’. The goal of the project was to determine the prevalence of manifest and potential drug

problems among long-term care facilities residents and to maximize the effectiveness and safety of their pharmacotherapy as a part of drug audit.

2 | Methodology

2.1 | Study Design and Participants

The project was designed as a multicentre, observational, descriptive study carried out in 16 nursing homes located in the Czech republic. In each case, a randomly selected sample of 50 community-dwelling people was included, i.e., the study was done on 800 participants in total. The study was carried out in accordance with The Code of Ethics of the World Medical Association (Declaration of Helsinki). Informed consent was obtained from all enrolled participants before entering the study. All participants met the entry criterion characterized by age ≥ 65 years. In each participant, a detailed analysis of chronic pharmacotherapy was carried out and evaluated in the context of his medical documentation, physical condition, subjective condition, and available laboratory tests received from the medical charts. The data were collected from the medical charts, and evaluation was carried out on a one-off basis aiming to assess the pattern of polypharmacy in Czech nursing homes. The participants were divided into two groups: with DRP identification (DRP+) and without DRP identification (DRP-). Identified drug problems were carefully recorded and classified according to the PCN international classification system and then assigned to a specific ATC group. A total of 20 clinical pharmacists participated in this project.

2.1.1 | Definitions

The term polypharmacy was defined as a regular use of five or more medications at the same time [15]. 'Overprescription' refers to an unclear (when the reason for the prescription was undetectable) or unnecessary (when the reason for the prescription was detectable) indication, whereas 'underprescription' to a new drug recommendation based on patients' medical records. The 'appropriateness' of the drug and dosage regimen were assessed in relation to patient's diagnosis, age, and renal and hepatic functions where available. The term contraindications means absolute contraindications, the official manufacturer's recommendation summarized in SmPC was strictly followed when assessing them. Drug-drug interactions were assessed using Lexicomp and then their clinical significance was assessed in the context of the patient's condition and further medication. Drug-disease interactions were defined as a medicine being used to treat one condition with the clearly documented potential to exacerbate a concurrent medical condition. Adverse drug events were defined in accordance with WHO as unwanted undesirable effects that are possibly related to a drug a response to a medicine which is noxious and unintended, and which occurs at doses normally used in man'. When assessing the adverse event as a possibly drug-related, the time course of the reaction, the dose of the drug (where potentially dose-dependent) and relevant susceptibility factors (such as genetic, pathological and other biological differences) were carefully considered. The recommendation for

laboratory monitoring was made in a patient using a drug or a combination of drugs resulting in a risk of DRP occurrence that could be clearly prevented early by adequate laboratory testing and where the required measurements were not available at all or they were performed with frequency not adequate considering the individual risk factors for DRP manifestation in a particular patient.

2.2 | Statistical Analysis

Descriptive analysis was used for statistical evaluation of the data. Continuous variables are presented as arithmetic mean \pm standard deviation, categorical variables as absolute or relative frequency [N (%)]. Continuous variables were compared by Student's *t*-test, categorical variables by chi-square test. The most common DRPs are presented in a graph along with absolute and relative frequency in our population. Drugs most frequently associated with DRPs in our dataset were identified and for each of them, odds ratio (OR), 95% confidence interval (CI) and *p*- (significance) were calculated. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analyses were used to calculate the area under the curve (AUC) for the number of used drugs to determine the best cut-off value for DRP identification. Sensitivity and specificity were calculated. The optimal cut-off point was obtained by using the Youden Index. For the identified cut-off, OR and 95% CI were calculated. A *p*-value ≤ 0.05 (two-tailed test) was considered statistically significant for all tests. Data were analyzed using the statistical MDCalc software (Medcalc version 22.026, Mariakerke, Belgium).

3 | Results

The average age of participants included was 84.6 ± 7.3 years; in terms of sex, women were more often represented (78.3%). The average BMI of the group was determined to be 25.7 ± 5.5 kg/m². A DRP was identified in a total of 746 (93.3%) clients. Of monitored variables, female sex (79.4% vs. 64.8%, $p=0.011$), polypharmacy (84.5% vs. 40.7%, $p<0.001$) and average number of medications (6.9 ± 2.1 vs. 3.9 ± 2.1 , $p<0.001$) were identified to be significantly associated with DRP occurrence. Frequency of DRPs was significantly higher in patients using 7–8 drugs (35.4% vs. 11.1%, $p<0.001$) and 9 or more drugs (24.8% vs. 0%, $p=0.012$). People with DRP suffered more frequently from cardiovascular disease (73.1% vs. 48.1%, $p<0.001$), neurological disease (60.3% vs. 37.0%, $p<0.001$) and depression/anxiety (35.9% vs. 14.8%, $p<0.001$) (Table 1).

A total of 2215 DRPs were identified in the study population, which represents 2.8 ± 1.6 problems on average per client. The analysis of individual recommendations showed that the most common drug problems were related to overprescribing [$N=433$ (19.5%)], underprescribing [$N=283$ (12.8%)], inappropriate dose [$N=235$ (10.6%)], recommendations for laboratory monitoring [$N=231$ (10.4%)] and adverse drug events [$N=228$ (10.3%)] (Figure 1). Of the analyzed DRPs, the number of drugs used was significantly associated with the following: overprescribing, adverse drug events, drug-drug interactions, drug-disease interactions, multiplicity, and drug formulation. For a detailed view of

TABLE 1 | Baseline characteristics of the study population.

	Total (N=800)	DRP+ (N=746)	DRP- (N=54)	p
Age	84.6±7.3	84.7±7.2	83.2±8.2	0.144
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.7±5.5	25.6±5.5	26.7±5.5	0.079
Female sex	627 (78.3)	592 (79.4)	35 (64.8)	0.011*
Number of medications	6.7±2.2	6.9±2.1	3.9±2.1	<0.001*
Polypharmacy	652 (81.5)	630 (84.5)	22 (40.7)	<0.001*
Number of medications – categories				
N<5	148 (18.5)	116 (15.5)	32 (59.3)	<0.001*
N=5–6	197 (24.6)	181 (24.3)	16 (29.7)	0.377
N=7–8	270 (33.8)	264 (35.4)	6 (11.1)	<0.001*
N>8	185 (23.1)	185 (24.8)	0 (0)	0.012*
Use of strong drug inhibitor/inducer	36 (4.5)	35 (4.7)	1 (1.9)	0.331
Comorbidities				
Cardiovascular disease	569 (71.1)	543 (73.1)	26 (48.1)	<0.001*
Dyslipidemia	351 (43.8)	330 (44.2)	21 (38.9)	0.585
Diabetes mellitus	182 (22.8)	170 (22.8)	12 (22.2)	0.923
COPD	55 (6.9)	52 (7.0)	3 (5.6)	0.692
Malignancy	52 (6.5)	48 (6.4)	4 (7.4)	0.067
Thyroid disease	110 (13.8)	102 (13.7)	8 (14.8)	0.810
Neurological disease	470 (58.8)	450 (60.3)	20 (37.0)	<0.001*
Depression/Anxiety	276 (34.5)	268 (35.9)	8 (14.8)	<0.001*

Note: Categorical variables are expressed as N (%). DRP+, population with identified drug-related problem; DRP-, population without identified drug-related problem. *Statistical significance for $p < 0.05$.

particular DRPs analysis and their association with monitored variables (see Table S1).

Table 2 summarizes drugs most commonly associated with DRP occurrence along with the corresponding types of DRPs. Namely, treatment with PPI (27.1% vs. 13.0%, OR 2.493, 95% CI 1.109–5.606), NSAIDs (14.5% vs. 3.7%, OR 4.401, 95% CI 1.056–18.336) and BDZ/Z-hypnotics (13.1% vs. 0%, OR 16.556, 95% CI 1.014–270.249) was identified to be significantly associated with DRP occurrence judging by OR calculation. Among the other drugs listed in Table 2 (warfarin, digoxin, potassium chloride supplements), only a trend to a higher frequency of DRPs was observed; the significance was not demonstrated.

The results of ROC analysis are shown in Figure 2 and Table 3. The ROC curve demonstrated that a total number of 7 drugs was the best cut-off for predicting DRP occurrence (AUC 0.842, sensitivity 0.602; specificity 0.796). For the identified cut-off, the calculated OR was 5.909 (95% CI 3.000–11.645).

4 | Discussion

In an effort to maximize the safety and effectiveness of pharmacotherapy, the data of a total of 800 Czech nursing home residents was systematically collected and evaluated over a period

of 4 years. We found a high prevalence of polypharmacy, with more than 80% of patients using more than five drugs. DRP was identified in 93.3% of participants, a finding consistent with available studies reporting detection of a drug problem in 82.7%–98.6% of nursing home residents [16–18]. The reported average numbers of DRP per patient are quite divergent in published studies, varying between 2.5 and 14.5 [18, 19]; however, due to the inconsistent methodology used in the classification of drug problems and in the evaluation of manifest and potential drug problems, it is not always possible to compare these values across studies. In our study, the average number of DRP per patient was 2.8 ± 1.6 , close to the average value of 2.5 DRP per patient reported in studies mapping the situation in nursing homes in the UK and Norway [19, 20].

As factors significantly associated with DRP occurrence, female sex and number of drugs used were identified in our population, as far as the comorbidities, cardiovascular disease, neurological disease, and depression/anxiety were those with significant association with DRP. The available literature states that women are, on average, 50%–75% more prone to manifestation of drugs' adverse effects because of sex-dependent differences in pharmacokinetics, in particular physiologically lower secretion of HCl, slightly slower gastrointestinal motility, a greater proportion of adipose tissue where the lipophilic drugs can be stored, usually a larger volume of distribution for hydrophilic drugs, slightly

Detailed analysis of identified DRPs

FIGURE 1 | Detailed analysis of identified DRPs (N=2215).

TABLE 2 | Drugs most commonly associated with DRP occurrences.

	DRP+ (N=746)	DRP- (N=54)	OR	95% CI	p	Most common types of DRPs
Warfarin	48 (6.4)	1 (1.9)	3.645	0.493–26.928	0.205	Adverse events, drug–drug interactions
Digoxin	36 (4.8)	1 (1.9)	2.687	0.361–19.987	0.334	Dose too high, TDM recommendation
KCl	46 (6.1)	2 (3.7)	1.774	0.419–7.508	0.436	Overprescription, recommendation for laboratory monitoring, drug–drug interactions
PPIs	202 (27.1)	7 (13.0)	2.493	1.109–5.606	0.027	Dose too high, overprescription
NSAIDs	108 (14.5)	2 (3.7)	4.401	1.056–18.336	0.042	Overprescribing, drug–drug and drug–disease interaction, contraindication
BDZ/Z-hypnotics	98 (13.1)	0 (0)	16.556	1.014–270.249	0.048	Overprescribing, inappropriate drug, adverse events

Note: DRP+, population with identified drug-related problem; DRP-, population without identified drug-related problem.

Abbreviations: 95% CI, 95% confidence interval; KCl, potassium chloride supplements; NSAIDs, non-steroidal antiinflammatory drugs; OR, odds ratio; PPI, proton pump inhibitor.

decelerated metabolism of some drugs, especially in the second phase of biotransformation, and on average 10%–25% reduced GFR even after correction for body weight [21]. All these factors predispose women to a higher prevalence of DRPs; however, further studies will be needed to validate these findings, especially among older people.

The number of medications taken has been repeatedly documented as an independent risk factor for DRPs occurrence although the exact cut-off associated with worse prognosis and mortality outcomes still remains the matter of debate, significantly depending on cohort characteristics [22, 23]. For

example, Gnjidic et al. aimed to determine an optimal discriminating number of concomitant medications for different adverse outcomes in a population of more than 1700 men aged 70 or more years [24]. For mortality and incident falls, they obtained the highest value of the Youden index for a cut-off of 4.5 medications, supporting the generally accepted definition for polypharmacy as five or more drugs used [15]. In our work, we focused on determining an optimal discriminating number associated with DRPs occurrence according to the sensitivity and specificity of this cut-off; the highest Youden index was obtained for seven or more drugs used associated with almost six times higher risk of DRPs occurrence. The risk clearly

increases with every increase in the number of drugs used as reported by Goldberg et al. [6]; the risk of adverse drug interactions occurrence rose from 13% in patients taking two medications to 82% in patients taking seven or more medications.

The most common DRP identified in the group was unclear (with an undetectable reason for the prescription), or unnecessary (if there is a detectable reason for the prescription) indication (19.5%). This finding is supported by the conclusions of a number of published studies, presenting ‘overtreatment’ as the most frequently detected DRP with a prevalence of up to 62.5% [17, 20, 25]. In contrast, the absence of a drug in a clear existing indication accounted for 12.8% of all detected DRPs, thus being classified as the second-most frequent DRP identified in the study population. Some of the available studies have concluded that ‘undertreatment’ represents the most frequent drug problem among residents of nursing homes with a reported prevalence of up to 37.7%, thus contradicting the assumption that the purpose of providing clinical pharmaceutical care is primarily to reduce the number of drugs used and cost of therapy [16]. Of the specific drug groups in our group, the most common were absent vitamin D and calcium in the prevention/therapy of osteoporosis and sarcopenia in mobile patients, missing antiplatelet therapy after acute coronary syndromes, missing anticoagulation in atrial fibrillation, and from other groups, for example, missing cholinesterase

inhibitors in Alzheimer's disease. In many cases (aspirin, cholecalciferol), these are very cheap drugs and their addition to medication can significantly improve the patient's long-term prognosis.

Inadequate dosing regimen accounted for 10.6% of all DRPs, which is consistent with the reported range of 4.2%–17.5% of all DRPs identified in nursing home residents [18, 26]. Altered pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic parameters in older persons often require dose reduction. The basic rule is to start therapy with low doses and gradually titrate to a therapeutic response; high-dose regimens can lead to drug accumulation and the development of adverse effects [27]. In 10.4% of DRPs, it was the absence of monitoring of basic biochemical and physiological parameters reflecting possible potential/manifest side effects of therapy, i.e., blood glucose with hypoglycemic medication, blood count with potentially hematotoxic drugs, ionogram with combined antihypertensive therapy, serum creatinine, liver tests, QTc for drugs with torsadogenic potential, etc. Among other drug problems, we noted drug adverse events (10.3%), inappropriate drug in relation to age, diagnosis, renal or hepatic functions where available (8.3%), drug–drug interactions (6.4%) etc.

Among the different drug classes, BDZ/Z-hypnotics, NSAIDs, and PPIs were identified to be significantly associated with DRP occurrence. We found a high prevalence of BDZ/Z-hypnotics use in our population reaching nearly 13%; although an even higher rate has been reported in other countries, we still consider it to be relatively high [28, 29]. Even though some patients in our population used them only occasionally, “as needed”, overall, we found their use was associated with nearly 17 times higher risk of DRP occurrence when compared to non-users. The problems associated with BDZ/Z-hypnotics overprescribing among older adults have been repeatedly documented even in the setting of only short-term use, as demonstrated in meta-analyses by Class et al.; short-term treatment with BDZ or Z-hypnotics (defined as at least for 5 consecutive nights, in majority of trials included for not more than 3 weeks) in people with insomnia aged 60 years or more led to improvement in sleep quality and an increase in total sleep time, but this was at the cost of significantly more adverse cognitive (OR 4.78, 1.47–15.47) and psychomotor (OR 2.61, 1.12–6.09) events when compared to placebo [30]. Furthermore, these drugs often persist in medication for a long time without a clear indication for their use. Maust et al. aimed to describe the

FIGURE 2 | Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) for the number of medications significantly associated with DRP occurrence.

TABLE 3 | Cut-off score and odds ratio for the number of medications associated with DRP occurrence.

Variable	AUC	Cut-off ^a (sensitivity; specificity)	OR for identified cut-off	95% CI	p
Number of medications	0.842	≥ 4 (0.980; 0.296)	20.519	9.442–44.594	<0.001
		≥ 5 (0.845; 0.482)	5.043	2.854–8.912	<0.001
		≥ 6 (0.716; 0.612)	3.958	2.239–6.998	<0.001
		≥ 7 (0.602; 0.796)	5.909	3.000–11.645	<0.001
		≥ 8 (0.389; 0.907)	6.232	2.454–15.826	<0.001
		≥ 9 (0.248; 1.000)	36.010	2.213–585.976	0.012

Abbreviations: 95% CI, 95% confidence interval; AUC, area under curve; OR, odds ratio.

^aOrdered by highest Youden index.

prescribing patterns for BDZ among U.S. patients aged 65 years and more who are seen by nonpsychiatrist physicians (i.e., BDZ prescribed by other specialists than psychiatrists). Among the continuation users, only 16.0% (95% CI=13.5–18.8) had any mental health diagnosis, mostly anxiety (6.4%), depression (5.0%) or insomnia (2.3%). The prevalence of mental health disorder was significantly higher in patients who had just received their first prescription (i.e., new-users), although still, the overall frequency was lower than expected (40.3%) [31]. These alarming findings call for the need for deprescribing of these drugs, especially among older people.

Despite the currently clearly decreasing trends in regular prescription of NSAIDs among community-dwelling older people, the overall prevalence of NSAIDs' use among older patients still remains high, apart from the others due to their OTC status [32]. In our population, their use on a regular or on-demand basis was found in more than 13% and was associated with more than four times higher risk of DRP when compared to non-users. Vandraas et al. also revealed a surprisingly high prevalence of chronic NSAIDs use (i.e., a treatment duration of at least 3 months) in older people co-medicated with drugs that may potentially interact with them; among all patients being chronically prescribed NSAIDs, almost 60% of them were concomitantly treated with drugs used for hypertension and/or heart failure and 35% with antithrombotic drugs [33]. According to Beers criteria 2023, chronic NSAIDs' use in general and short-term scheduled NSAIDs' use in case of combination with corticosteroids or antithrombotic drugs should be avoided unless other alternatives are not effective and the patient can take a gastroprotective agent. During treatment with NSAIDs, careful surveillance to monitor gastrointestinal, renal, and cardiovascular toxicity is crucial [34].

PPIs belong to one of the most widely overprescribed medications worldwide [35]. The prevalence of their use among older adults is reported in a wide range varying between 12.6% and 79.7%. In our population, their use was documented in around 26% of all participants, a similar proportion to the one reported in older nursing home residents in the US (26.99%) [36]. Importantly, this cross-sectional study also revealed that nearly half of all the prescribed PPIs were not evidence-based. This—taken together with their problematic safety profile for older people, including the increased risk of osteoporosis-related fractures, *Clostridium difficile* infection, community-acquired pneumonia, vitamin B deficiency, and possibly higher risk for dementia and kidney disease—makes them one of the most common causes of DRP, as demonstrated by several trials mapping the situation in older nursing home residents [18, 37–40]. We found their use was associated with almost 2.5 times higher risk of DRP occurrence when compared to non-users. These findings are supported by the decision of the American Geriatrics Society to update Beers Criteria in 2015 recommending avoiding scheduled use of PPIs for > 8 weeks in older adults, except in high-risk patients [41].

In the present study, we confirmed the high rate of polypharmacy associated with DRPs among older residents of Czech nursing homes, which is in accordance with reports from other countries documenting a need for a proactive approach and regular reassessment of medication in this population. We support the previously published expert's recommendation for regular

review of older people's medication; i.e., at least annually for people receiving fewer than four drugs and at least every 6 months for those taking four or more drugs [42]. Clinical pharmacists' interventions have been documented to improve compliance, safety, and cost-effectiveness of therapy, and in several trials, they were also suggested to reduce mortality among patients receiving polypharmacy [43–46]. Thus, they have been recommended to be integrated into interdisciplinary cooperation with other health-care providers in long-term care facilities by many authors and some national guidelines as well [47–49]. Our findings confirm the crucial role of clinical pharmacists as an integral part of the multidisciplinary team in regular medication reviews and subsequent suggestions of specific pharmacotherapy measures to be adopted by the attending physician. To our knowledge, this is the first project of a similar scope systematically mapping DRPs in long-term care facilities in the Czech Republic.

4.1 | Limitations

Our study has several limitations. Not all the nursing home residents' medication was assessed; however, the sample of 50 patients was always randomly selected in each of the 16 Czech nursing homes included; thus, we believe the generalizability of the results should not be affected. Incompleteness of medical records, especially the lack of current laboratory measurements in some patients, was another limitation. The drug interactions/adverse events are presented as a cumulative account for both potential and manifested reactions, and they were often recorded only on a self-reported basis, which might be subjected to recall bias. We did not assess other covariates with potential independent impact on DRPs occurrence; thus, the demonstrated relationship between risk factors and DRPs must be interpreted with caution. The inconsistent methodology used in the DRPs assessments among different studies leads to limited comparability with findings of other authors.

5 | Conclusion

Our project has confirmed a high rate of excessive polypharmacy among nursing home residents in the Czech Republic, resulting in a high risk of potential and manifested DRPs. The project emphasized the role of clinical pharmacists in optimizing the safety and effectiveness of treatment among older persons in nursing home residences, and it helped to convince the Czech regulatory authorities to establish the position of clinical pharmacist as a healthcare provider in social care settings.

Author Contributions

M.H., M.M. wrote the manuscript; M.H., D.Č., V.Š. designed the research; M.H., D.Č., Z.K. performed the research; M.M., I.P. analyzed the data.

Acknowledgments

The project has been carried out in close collaboration with the State Institute for Drug Control and Na Homolce Hospital, without whose support it could not have been started and further developed. We can only express our sincere thanks and hope that their support of the project

will persist. The project is supported by the Czech Society of General Practice, Society of Physicians and Medical Staff in Social Services, and Geriatric Society CzMA JEP. In the project, we actively collaborate with all these subjects and coordinate our activities with theirs.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.